

Popular Article

Role of Microbiologists in controlling Covid-19 Pandemic

Mehak Tikoo and Deep Shikha*

* Division of Veterinary Microbiology and Immunology, FVSc & AH., SKUAST-Jammu

DOI:

Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic is a global coronavirus disease pandemic that began in 2019 and is caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2. (SARS CoV-2). An epidemic in Wuhan, China, was the catalyst for the discovery of this new virus. It has caused significant financial hardship and death, making it one of the deadliest viruses in history. The structural and functional features of this virus must be identified in order to diagnose and treat it early. As a result, microbiologists play a critical role in preventing the spread of this disease.

Keywords: SARS CoV-2, Diagnostic kits, Antiviral therapy, Vaccines, Biomedical waste

Introduction

The first cases of SARS-CoV2 in India were reported on 30th January 2020 in Kerala. Since then, the destruction and devastation caused by this virus have resulted in monetary as well as loss of precious lives in various regions of our country. Because the virus is new, it must be identified and classified before strategic control strategies can be developed. As a result, microbiologists play a critical role.

Microbiologists are those scientists which study about the microscopic life forms and processes. Microbiologists have played a great role in identifying the SARS-CoV2 virus, developing a diagnostic toolkit for detection, generation of vaccines and in developing effective antiviral therapy for the disease. Microbiologists have been regarded as one of the crucial covid warriors fighting against the spread of the disease. Tests like RT-PCR, Rapid Antigen Test etc. have been proven to aid in the diagnosis of this disease. Furthermore, next generation sequencing techniques are also being used for genomic identification of this novel virus.

Role of Microbiologists:

Collection of specimens and its transportation

Only after following the case definition provided by the health authorities, Government of India, may the clinician decide on the need for clinical specimen collection for 2019-nCoV laboratory testing. In the presence of a clinician, a suitable clinical sample must be taken by laboratory personnel/healthcare workers who have been trained in specimen collection. Clinical samples must be sent to the approved laboratory such as (ICMR-NIV, Pune) using standard triple packing while adhering to all biosafety measures and wearing personal protective equipment (PPEs). Anyone who has Severe Acute Respiratory Illness (SARI) AND one or more of the following: a history of travel from Wuhan, China in the 14 days prior to onset of symptoms; disease in a healthcare worker who works in an environment with SARI patients; unusual or unexpected clinical course, especially sudden deterioration despite appropriate treatment; should be investigated immediately.

Laboratory diagnosis of Covid-19

SARS-CoV-2 genetic material or humoral responses are identified in tests for the etiological agent. Identifying viral genome targets in respiratory tract materials using real-time polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) within the first week of symptoms is the gold standard for diagnosis. Serological tests should be ordered starting the second week after the onset of symptoms. There are many different tests available, each with a distinct sensitivity and specificity, and the majority of them require validation. Complete blood count, C-reactive protein (CRP), D-dimer, clotting tests, lactic dehydrogenase (LDH), ferritin, and procalcitonin are examples of laboratory tests that can identify the risk of disease with greater severity, thromboembolic consequences, cardiac damage, and/or a poor prognosis. Imaging scans can help with diagnosis, especially if the clinical picture is consistent and other tests have come up negative or are unavailable (Goudouris E. S. *et al.*, 2021).

Mass screening of suspected Covid-19 population by Rapid Antigen test

Early detection is still as important as it was in the early stages of the COVID-19 pandemic. Because RT-PCR is not always possible in developing countries or rural locations, doctors may utilise a rapid antigen test (RAT) to reduce the burden of diagnosis. The effectiveness of RAT, on the other hand, has yet to be properly examined. The total pooled specificity and sensitivity of RAT were found to be 99.4% (95 percent CI: 99.1–99.8; I2 = 90 percent) and 68.4% (95 percent CI: 60.8–75.9; I2 = 98 percent) in one study, respectively. Nasopharyngeal specimens and samples from symptomatic patients were shown to be more

sensitive in RAT, while cycle threshold (Ct) values were found to have an inverse connection with sensitivity in subgroup analysis. RAT performed better in both European and American populations. Although RAT's sensitivity needs to be enhanced, it could still be a viable option in places where laboratory facilities are lacking. However, to reduce false negative results, RAT negative samples can be re-tested using RT-PCR (Khandker, S. S. et al., 2021).

Development and Production of Covid-19 vaccines

Microbiologists have played an important role in development of vaccines. They have aided in identifying the SARS CoV2 structure, its potency, immunogenic properties etc and thus have opened a gateway for development of vaccines. COVID-19 vaccine candidates in development and clinical testing in India are among the most advanced products in the world. Apart from the COVID-19 vaccines developed in India, other local pharmaceutical and biotech companies have inked collaboration arrangements with vaccine developers from other countries. This cooperation vary from clinical trials through vaccine manufacture and distribution on a wide scale. Few covid vaccines developed in our country include Covishield, Covaxin, ZyCoV-D, Novavax, and others.

Development of high sensitivity and specificity-based tests

Several new high sensitivity and specificity tests have been developed to accurately diagnose the SARS-CoV-2. These tests include rRT-PCR, LAMP, Lateral Flow, ELISA etc. These tests use specimens like nasopharyngeal swab samples and blood for diagnosis. The time for production of results can vary from 20 min- 4 hours (Younes, N. *et al.*, 2020).

Development of antiviral therapy

For those who are awaiting vaccination as well as those who do not respond well to vaccination, the discovery of effective antiviral medication for COVID-19 is crucial. The sole medicine licenced by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for the treatment of COVID-19 is Remdesivir. The FDA has granted Emergency Use Authorizations for ritonavir-boosted nirmatrelvir (Paxlovid), molnupiravir, and some anti-SARS-CoV-2 monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) for the treatment of COVID-19.

Biomedical waste management

All waste generated during diagnostic testing of suspected covid-19 patients is referred to as Covid-19 biomedical waste. This includes patient samples (nasopharyngeal swabs, blood, sputum), laboratory reagents and consumables (disposable syringes, needles, and cotton swabs), and laboratory worker protective gear (coverall suits, gloves, N95 masks, face shield, and so on). Color-coded bins/bags/containers should be used for proper waste disposal. Double-layered bags

must be used to collect waste from the sample collection room as a precaution. Before being delivered to a local biomedical waste facility, all microbiology laboratory waste should be autoclaved at a waste management complex.

Conclusion

SARS CoV2 is a novel virus which is mutating rapidly with time and resulting in emergence of new variants. Thus, thorough studying, identification and classification of such variants is necessary. Microbiologists all over the world have been conducting research regarding the properties, infectivity, potency etc of this virus. These research aid in developing diagnostic kits, production of vaccines and generation of effective antiviral therapy against this disease. As a result, microbiologists play a critical role in today's world. It is also critical to establish new research and diagnostic laboratory facilities in order to diagnose the virus effectively and quickly.

References

- Covid-19 biomedical waste guidelines, Central pollution control board, Ministry of environment, forest and climate change, Govt of India.
- Goudouris, E. S. 2021. Laboratory diagnosis of COVID-19. *Jornal de pediatria*, 97(1): 7–12.
- Khandker, S. S., Nik Hashim, N., Deris, Z. Z., Shueb, R. H. and Islam, M. A. 2021. Diagnostic Accuracy of Rapid Antigen Test Kits for Detecting SARS-CoV-2: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of 17,171 Suspected COVID-19 Patients. *Journal of clinical medicine*, 10(16): 3493.
- Specimen Collection, Packaging and Transport Guidelines for 2019 novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV)
https://www.mohfw.gov.in/pdf/5Sample%20collection_packaging%20%202019-nCoV.pdf
- www.covid19treatmentguidelines.nih.gov
- Younes, N., Al-Sadeq, D. W., Al-Jighefee, H., Younes, S., Al-Jamal, O., Daas, H. I., Yassine, H. M. and Nasrallah, G. K. 2020. Challenges in Laboratory Diagnosis of the Novel Coronavirus SARS-CoV-2. *Viruses*, 12(6): 582.